

Occurrence of white tip disease in deepwater rice in Bangladesh

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Rice white tip disease, caused by the nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi* Christie 1942, was reported near Dacca in 1955 but its distribution in other deepwater rice areas and the extent of crop and yield damage in Bangladesh are unknown. In 1981 white tip was found in the Manikganj, Narshingdi, and Chandina deepwater rice areas. Samples were taken at booting stage and examined for nematodes. About 60% of the rice fields in Manikganj were infested. New symptoms induced by this nematode and its influence on some plant characters including yield components were recorded.

Chlorotic discoloration on the leaf base just below the collar at 2- to 3-leaf stage of the seedling and splash patterned chlorosis or chlorotic stripes on the innermost leaf with a whitish tip at the elongating stage of the crop were disease symptoms. The flag leaf of the infected plant was shortened, twisted, crinkled, and often distorted or split longitudinally. The panicle emerged partially or completely and had whitish spikelets on the tip or throughout.

In a preliminary survey, the local deepwater rice variety Rajboalia was highly susceptible to white tip nematode. It was examined to assess nematode population in rice grains and influence on panicle length, panicle weight, and some yield components. Ten panicles with white tip symptoms and 10 healthy panicles were sampled from each of 10 different fields. Panicle length and weight were measured. Filled and sterile grains were counted, then grains were threshed and bulked separately. One thousand grains from each bulk sample were weighed and nematode population in 100 grains was estimated by soaking split grains overnight and examining and counting nematodes under a microscope.

Population density of white tip nematode in rice grains and its influence on panicle length, panicle weight, and yield components in deepwater rice variety Rajboalia, Bangladesh, 1981.

Character	Healthy plant	Diseased plant	Mean difference ^a
Nematode population/100 grains	112	650	538**
Panicle weight (g)	5.7	1.9	3.7**
Panicle length (cm)	30.0	23.0	7.0**
Filled grains/panicle	173	47	126**
Sterile grains/panicle (%)	21.8	77.2	55.4**
1,000-grain weight (g)	18.1	5.5	12.6**

^a**All differences are statistically significant (*t*-test) $p = 0.01$.

Panicles from plants with white tip symptoms were significantly shorter, weighed less, had fewer filled grains and

lower 1,000-grain weight. There were significantly more nematodes per 100 grains (see table).

In vitro toxicity of some fermented oil cake extracts to *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Sclerotium oryzae*

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Applying some nonedible oil cakes is thought to increase some soil antagonist populations. We studied the effect of oil cakes commonly used by Indian farmers on in vitro inhibition of *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Sclerotium oryzae*, which cause rice sheath blight and stem rot.

Two hundred grams each of kusum *Schleichera trijuga*; mohuwa *Bassia latifolia*; neem *Melia azadirachtae*; and sal *Schorea robusta* were placed in plastic mug and fermented for 25 days in irrigation water. Contents were then filtered and the supernatant was centrifuged. The resultant solution was adjusted to 200 ml stock solution by flash evaporation. The stock solution was added to potato dextrose agar (PDA) media in different concentrations (see table) and autoclaved. Nutrient concentration (potato decoction and glucose) for all

Growth inhibition of *R. solani* and *S. oryzae* in fermented oil cake extracts, Hyderabad, India.

Oil cake	Concentration		<i>R. solani</i> colony diameter (cm)	PI ^a	<i>S. oryzae</i> colony diameter (cm)	PI ^a
	Medium	Extract				
Kusum	180	20	3.8	57.7	1.4	72.7
	160	40	1.3	85.6	1.0	83.6
	140	60	0.8	91.1	0	100.0
	120	80	0	100.0	0	100.0
Mohuwa	180	20	4.6	48.9	1.1	80.0
	160	40	4.6	48.9	0.7	87.2
	140	60	4.3	53.3	0	100.0
	120	80	4.1	54.4	0	100.0
Neem	180	20	4.5	50.0	0	100.0
	160	40	2.8	69.0	0	100.0
	140	60	2.0	77.8	0	100.0
	120	80	0.8	100.0	0	100.0
Sal	180	20	3.4	62.2	3.9	29.1
	160	40	2.5	73.3	3.7	32.7
	140	60	0	100.0	3.1	45.5
	120	80	0	100.0	2.0	63.6
Control	Potato dextrose agar		9.0	—	5.5	—
	C.D. for colony diameter		0.31	C.D. for colony diameter	0.19	
	C.V.		7.76%	C.V.	10.35%	

^aPercentage of growth inhibition (PI) over check.

treatments was constant. Poison-food technique was used to study growth inhibition of the two pathogens.

The media was plated into petri dishes and dried for 24 hours. Plates were inoculated with *R. solani* and *S. oryzae*

growth disks. PDA plates without any extract were used as control. Colony diameter was measured 3 days after inoculation.

Results (see table) showed the pathogens were inhibited at all oil cake extract

concentrations. *R. solani* growth inhibition was greater in sal cake extract followed by that in kusum, neem, and mohuwa extracts. *S. oryzae* growth was completely inhibited at all neem cake extract concentrations. *k*

Occurrence of brown spot in rice in relation to nutritional soil status

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Brown spot, caused by *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito and Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Datsur, severely damaged Mahsuri variety during the 1978 dry season in the Operational Research Project Village of Kandarpur in Cuttack, Orissa.

Fields of Mahsuri in five villages — Athanga, Kandarpur, Fakirpara, Sidheswarpur, and Deopur — were tested

for disease severity. A nine-point scale was used to score disease damage. Observations were made at maximum tillering and 1 month before harvest. More than 14 spots per leaf were counted. In Athanga, rice leaves had type C lesions or small spots. In other villages disease intensity was not so severe. Severity varied with soil nutritional status (see table). Percentages of organic carbon, nitrogen, and potash, and cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the soil were very low in Athanga. Seed was sown late and there was an irrigation water shortage.

In the other villages, disease incidence

was low. Percentages of organic carbon and nitrogen in the soil were medium. Potash and CEC levels in the soil were low. Planting was done on time and there was irrigation water.

Disease incidence was lowest in Deopur. Soil pH was acidic, organic carbon medium, and total nitrogen slightly higher than in other fields.

The present study indicates brown spot occurrences are most severe in soils with high pH, low organic carbon percentage, low nitrogen and potash levels, low CEC and under dry conditions which cause low plant nutrient availability. *k*

Occurrence of brown spot on rice variety Mahsuri at different soil fertility levels and sites, Orissa, India.

Site	pH	Organic carbon (%)	Total N (%)	Olsen P (ppm)	CEC (meq/100 g soil)	Exchangeable cations (meq/100 g soil)			Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Disease intensity ^a	
						K	Ca	Mg			Maximum tillering stage	1 mo before harvest
Athanga	6.3	0.44	0.040	7	7.60	0.051	4.55	1.233	9	20	8.92	9.00
Kandarpur	6.1	0.58	0.040	6	7.10	0.051	4.00	1.183	16	32	3.40	3.72
Fakirpara	6.6	0.56	0.048	9	10.40	0.102	7.45	1.850	12	20	3.68	4.20
Sidheswarpur	5.6	0.50	0.029	10	9.70	0.051	5.20	2.733	13	48	4.76	5.16
Deopur	5.5	0.70	0.063	6	12.00	0.193	4.30	1.523	11	30	1.96	2.68

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9: 1 = less than 1% incidence, 9 = 76-100%.

Echinochloa colona, an alternate host of *Sarocladium oryzae* causing sheath rot of rice

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Sheath rot caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw) Gem. is a major disease in Bangladesh. It was first observed in 1973.

During the 1980 boro season (spring rice, harvested in April), rice field weed *Echinochloa colona* (L) Link was found growing near an infected hill of variety BR3, a variety moderately susceptible to sheath rot. Infected BR3 tillers and the culm of the weed were close to each other. The leaf sheaths of

1. Typical symptoms of rice (left) and *E. colona* (right) infected with *S. oryzae*.

the weed were infected. Symptoms were similar to rice sheath rot except that lesions were lighter brown and had whitish mycelia and fungus spores (Fig. 1 and 2).

Infected rice hills and weed plants were collected to isolate the causal organism(s). Growth characters and morphology of the fungal colony isolated from the weed were similar to those of the colony isolated from the rice. Fungi from rice and weed were identified as *S. oryzae*. Isolated organisms were cross-inoculated in potted BR3 and *E. colona* plants. In 15-20 days BR3 and *E. colona* produced symptoms similar to those observed in the field.